
Article

Anticancer Effects of Alpelisib on PIK3CA-mutated Canine Mammary Tumor Cell Lines

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Table S1. Cytotoxicity of alpelisib against VCL for 24 h.

Alpelisib (μ M)	VCL002	VCL004	VCL005	VCL006	VCL007	VCL008	VCL009	VCL010	VCL011	VCL012
0	99.974 $\pm$ 5.659	100.024 $\pm$ 4.334	99.971 $\pm$ 9.420	100.000 $\pm$ 2.859	100.023 $\pm$ 1.641	99.924 $\pm$ 2.971	100.000 $\pm$ 3.097	100.018 $\pm$ 3.949	100.015 $\pm$ 1.908	100.055 $\pm$ 4.212
0.01	103.279 $\pm$ 2.211	95.528 $\pm$ 8.109	86.018 $\pm$ 7.095	113.103 $\pm$ 5.413	86.059 $\pm$ 6.255	97.945 $\pm$ 5.398	83.792 $\pm$ 4.562	101.524 $\pm$ 3.532	92.834 $\pm$ 7.140	115.525 $\pm$ 7.338
0.05	99.010 $\pm$ 3.550	93.192 $\pm$ 11.953	94.057 $\pm$ 3.448	113.333 $\pm$ 2.700	83.262 $\pm$ 6.166	93.455 $\pm$ 0.923	98.197 $\pm$ 11.355	107.787 $\pm$ 4.236	92.714 $\pm$ 5.084	119.144 $\pm$ 9.527
0.1	106.204 $\pm$ 7.651	87.100 $\pm$ 18.090	98.668 $\pm$ 6.795	110.345 $\pm$ 3.128	70.399 $\pm$ 9.513	90.868 $\pm$ 4.718	101.989 $\pm$ 13.086	113.664 $\pm$ 7.455	87.377 $\pm$ 3.345	122.451 $\pm$ 16.909
0.5	84.225 $\pm$ 3.933	75.236 $\pm$ 15.640	73.832 $\pm$ 2.394	100.805 $\pm$ 3.814	59.933 $\pm$ 2.751	89.193 $\pm$ 3.719	89.619 $\pm$ 11.043	108.650 $\pm$ 10.888	73.288 $\pm$ 2.190	114.903 $\pm$ 13.825
1	61.252 $\pm$ 2.809	69.381 $\pm$ 0.643	52.954 $\pm$ 3.770	102.492 $\pm$ 3.720	47.912 $\pm$ 4.876	80.897 $\pm$ 7.077	69.402 $\pm$ 9.693	81.642 $\pm$ 3.602	55.480 $\pm$ 1.345	90.328 $\pm$ 7.087
5	57.518 $\pm$ 4.172	42.814 $\pm$ 3.427	51.707 $\pm$ 3.278	80.575 $\pm$ 2.322	43.569 $\pm$ 1.545	80.213 $\pm$ 4.845	38.382 $\pm$ 0.992	79.008 $\pm$ 1.889	52.048 $\pm$ 3.987	103.463 $\pm$ 10.996
10	43.612 $\pm$ 2.020	42.524 $\pm$ 2.830	45.086 $\pm$ 5.114	92.069 $\pm$ 4.353	41.677 $\pm$ 3.413	82.135 $\pm$ 9.185	38.167 $\pm$ 2.190	68.612 $\pm$ 3.749	50.286 $\pm$ 2.145	83.224 $\pm$ 3.990
25	36.678 $\pm$ 1.693	39.512 $\pm$ 1.522	41.340 $\pm$ 5.345	90.257 $\pm$ 6.089	42.394 $\pm$ 2.277	77.262 $\pm$ 3.798	40.315 $\pm$ 1.856	58.741 $\pm$ 4.079	49.307 $\pm$ 3.794	75.191 $\pm$ 2.849
50	34.436 $\pm$ 1.693	35.476 $\pm$ 0.835	40.778 $\pm$ 4.604	84.894 $\pm$ 8.281	42.313 $\pm$ 1.517	78.036 $\pm$ 7.773	41.676 $\pm$ 1.898	59.456 $\pm$ 2.288	48.238 $\pm$ 3.322	70.383 $\pm$ 4.671
100	33.368 $\pm$ 1.987	31.488 $\pm$ 1.287	38.228 $\pm$ 2.008	81.118 $\pm$ 5.430	39.398 $\pm$ 1.931	73.312 $\pm$ 5.694	37.809 $\pm$ 2.977	57.565 $\pm$ 3.526	46.868 $\pm$ 4.256	61.530 $\pm$ 5.095

Table S2. Cytotoxicity of alpelisib against VCL for 48 h.

Alpelisib (μM)	VCL002	VCL004	VCL005	VCL006	VCL007	VCL008	VCL009	VCL010	VCL011	VCL012
0	99.989 $\pm$ 2.771	100.000 $\pm$ 3.964	99.987 $\pm$ 17.155	100.080 $\pm$ 9.313	100.009 $\pm$ 0.653	99.909 $\pm$ 0.316	100.015 $\pm$ 1.791	100.000 $\pm$ 3.020	99.987 $\pm$ 1.381	99.950 $\pm$ 7.343
0.01	105.309 $\pm$ 3.942	90.209 $\pm$ 3.462	98.156 $\pm$ 4.287	109.829 $\pm$ 1.880	83.265 $\pm$ 3.433	106.393 $\pm$ 3.954	89.443 $\pm$ 6.402	94.428 $\pm$ 9.640	101.497 $\pm$ 2.556	101.702 $\pm$ 13.024
0.05	101.519 $\pm$ 3.767	86.092 $\pm$ 7.942	95.247 $\pm$ 8.058	111.257 $\pm$ 4.168	70.429 $\pm$ 4.237	109.224 $\pm$ 2.604	100.442 $\pm$ 12.270	102.425 $\pm$ 4.209	96.966 $\pm$ 6.718	99.652 $\pm$ 12.201
0.1	97.025 $\pm$ 2.092	81.366 $\pm$ 6.001	89.210 $\pm$ 4.771	106.457 $\pm$ 5.057	57.837 $\pm$ 4.557	106.210 $\pm$ 8.648	104.821 $\pm$ 16.921	102.440 $\pm$ 10.208	95.376 $\pm$ 3.031	101.315 $\pm$ 15.189
0.5	74.543 $\pm$ 4.185	84.058 $\pm$ 6.194	63.447 $\pm$ 2.996	98.000 $\pm$ 3.084	44.776 $\pm$ 3.823	95.799 $\pm$ 3.175	87.933 $\pm$ 12.986	94.111 $\pm$ 8.956	77.530 $\pm$ 1.115	105.493 $\pm$ 16.466
1	48.183 $\pm$ 3.795	72.952 $\pm$ 2.218	37.640 $\pm$ 6.015	97.356 $\pm$ 3.937	38.324 $\pm$ 1.114	92.031 $\pm$ 5.185	64.027 $\pm$ 6.827	67.421 $\pm$ 5.134	54.756 $\pm$ 1.968	92.903 $\pm$ 5.567
5	44.716 $\pm$ 1.134	39.462 $\pm$ 4.796	35.269 $\pm$ 2.647	71.086 $\pm$ 6.970	31.847 $\pm$ 3.284	79.087 $\pm$ 2.214	42.533 $\pm$ 4.131	66.521 $\pm$ 2.399	43.680 $\pm$ 7.179	80.271 $\pm$ 8.174
10	28.612 $\pm$ 2.033	37.222 $\pm$ 4.195	30.621 $\pm$ 3.009	89.503 $\pm$ 5.981	31.819 $\pm$ 1.446	88.047 $\pm$ 5.272	33.065 $\pm$ 2.556	53.875 $\pm$ 2.038	42.991 $\pm$ 1.352	83.077 $\pm$ 5.065
25	22.379 $\pm$ 1.131	29.716 $\pm$ 2.842	28.588 $\pm$ 2.059	91.667 $\pm$ 11.759	29.964 $\pm$ 0.679	91.837 $\pm$ 7.159	32.503 $\pm$ 3.031	43.296 $\pm$ 1.990	37.918 $\pm$ 3.222	76.576 $\pm$ 4.360
50	18.557 $\pm$ 1.374	25.575 $\pm$ 1.818	30.358 $\pm$ 2.521	82.212 $\pm$ 11.421	30.358 $\pm$ 1.158	89.504 $\pm$ 3.362	29.970 $\pm$ 3.447	40.746 $\pm$ 1.263	38.011 $\pm$ 1.851	65.608 $\pm$ 3.770
100	18.293 $\pm$ 1.339	23.664 $\pm$ 2.772	29.090 $\pm$ 2.362	71.554 $\pm$ 3.406	26.281 $\pm$ 1.269	84.159 $\pm$ 9.385	25.588 $\pm$ 2.086	39.863 $\pm$ 2.985	31.462 $\pm$ 1.098	57.767 $\pm$ 5.423

Table S3. Cytotoxicity of alpelisib against VCL for 72 h.

Alpelisib (μ M)	VCL002	VCL004	VCL005	VCL006	VCL007	VCL008	VCL009	VCL010	VCL011	VCL012
0	100.024 $\pm$ 2.384	99.991 $\pm$ 1.782	99.976 $\pm$ 14.666	99.856 $\pm$ 3.151	99.979 $\pm$ 4.710	99.891 $\pm$ 6.082	100.000 $\pm$ 2.072	99.986 $\pm$ 5.262	100.012 $\pm$ 0.458	99.875 $\pm$ 7.613
0.01	96.077 $\pm$ 5.926	102.570 $\pm$ 3.452	95.068 $\pm$ 4.004	124.854 $\pm$ 4.549	81.013 $\pm$ 7.276	88.358 $\pm$ 2.550	80.537 $\pm$ 3.894	97.589 $\pm$ 8.280	97.072 $\pm$ 5.287	93.642 $\pm$ 9.005
0.05	94.751 $\pm$ 6.627	92.309 $\pm$ 6.413	86.721 $\pm$ 2.992	123.333 $\pm$ 4.480	74.487 $\pm$ 6.530	85.871 $\pm$ 4.491	81.729 $\pm$ 4.304	109.196 $\pm$ 6.728	101.635 $\pm$ 2.946	99.457 $\pm$ 6.641
0.1	95.329 $\pm$ 3.947	91.084 $\pm$ 5.014	81.687 $\pm$ 4.055	111.404 $\pm$ 5.756	71.222 $\pm$ 6.786	91.741 $\pm$ 1.799	80.698 $\pm$ 5.008	103.883 $\pm$ 12.165	99.353 $\pm$ 2.037	105.304 $\pm$ 9.748
0.5	70.700 $\pm$ 2.652	83.777 $\pm$ 10.347	54.080 $\pm$ 4.381	98.830 $\pm$ 3.863	47.901 $\pm$ 2.664	88.557 $\pm$ 4.370	70.741 $\pm$ 4.855	97.289 $\pm$ 3.443	89.239 $\pm$ 2.474	104.026 $\pm$ 8.626
1	48.859 $\pm$ 3.147	70.941 $\pm$ 5.325	36.364 $\pm$ 3.661	98.851 $\pm$ 2.516	38.843 $\pm$ 2.055	62.963 $\pm$ 3.140	48.808 $\pm$ 6.255	68.378 $\pm$ 5.338	68.311 $\pm$ 0.946	99.687 $\pm$ 6.549
5	36.644 $\pm$ 1.361	36.927 $\pm$ 3.914	31.150 $\pm$ 1.199	77.135 $\pm$ 6.242	30.149 $\pm$ 3.415	70.945 $\pm$ 5.086	31.408 $\pm$ 6.168	73.842 $\pm$ 1.672	51.025 $\pm$ 4.692	83.930 $\pm$ 2.655
10	29.358 $\pm$ 2.261	34.402 $\pm$ 2.589	30.145 $\pm$ 3.167	83.405 $\pm$ 5.280	28.822 $\pm$ 0.842	67.865 $\pm$ 2.929	26.439 $\pm$ 0.751	53.990 $\pm$ 3.236	45.189 $\pm$ 2.769	89.404 $\pm$ 7.426
25	22.747 $\pm$ 1.962	28.438 $\pm$ 2.089	30.618 $\pm$ 3.023	80.819 $\pm$ 3.964	25.615 $\pm$ 1.419	73.638 $\pm$ 3.224	26.380 $\pm$ 1.422	43.492 $\pm$ 2.973	37.347 $\pm$ 1.402	83.574 $\pm$ 3.381
50	16.266 $\pm$ 1.374	21.114 $\pm$ 0.603	28.279 $\pm$ 2.682	74.210 $\pm$ 9.046	23.764 $\pm$ 0.688	80.065 $\pm$ 4.323	23.591 $\pm$ 2.714	44.784 $\pm$ 3.149	35.187 $\pm$ 2.270	81.254 $\pm$ 6.460
100	14.507 $\pm$ 1.395	19.169 $\pm$ 0.625	25.394 $\pm$ 2.672	76.437 $\pm$ 6.988	20.789 $\pm$ 0.990	75.490 $\pm$ 2.143	20.507 $\pm$ 0.156	47.417 $\pm$ 3.426	31.149 $\pm$ 1.640	67.210 $\pm$ 5.723

Figure S1. The migration of MDCK was measured by the wound healing assay after formation of scratch and 24 h treatment of various concentrations of alpelisib (0, 1, 5 and 10 μM).